

Research Article

My Driving Application

Nik Mohd Faris Nik Min¹, Ayu Kamareenna Abdullah Thani^{2,*}, Nurul Aina Najiha Yahya³, Syifaa Abdul Rashid⁴, Siti Nor Ain Mohd Navi⁵, Nur Afiqah Mohamad Arif⁶, and Nurul Najwa Hanani Muhammad⁷

¹ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; nikfaris@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-4424-597X

² Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; ayukamareenna@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0001-7851-2354

³ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan

⁴ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan

⁵ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan

* Correspondence: ayukamareenna@uitm.edu.my; 019-9034261.

Abstract: "My Driving App" is an innovative e-booking platform designed to streamline the booking and scheduling process for driving classes. Currently, users face inefficiencies and irregular schedules, hindering the learning experience. Our app addresses these issues by providing real-time class vacancy updates for students and simplifying date confirmations for staff. This user-friendly system enhances operational efficiency and ensures a smoother booking experience. Unique in its comprehensive approach, "My Driving App" has significant commercialization potential, catering to driving schools seeking to modernize and optimize their class management processes.

Keywords: e booking platform, driving schools, class management processes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional methods for booking and scheduling driving classes are fraught with inefficiencies, negatively affecting both students and driving schools. These issues include irregular schedules, overbooking, under booking, communication gaps, and a substantial administrative workload (Rachmawati et al., 2022). Resolving these problems is crucial to improving the student learning experience, enhancing operational efficiency for driving schools, and boosting revenue through optimized class occupancy. Recent statistics and studies highlight the pressing need to modernize driving school operations (Deppermen, 2018).

In Malaysia, driving classes and licensing regulations have seen significant updates in recent years. As of September 15, 2023, the Transport Ministry introduced a new policy where individuals who have already passed the KPP01 theory test for either a motorcycle or car license do not need to retake the test when applying for the other type of license. This change aims to save time and reduce costs for applicants, eliminating the need for a second six-hour theory class and saving approximately RM100 for each applicant. "My Driving App" effectively addresses these needs by providing a comprehensive, real-time booking and scheduling platform, thereby improving the learning experience and operational efficiency, making it a timely and essential advancement for the driving education industry.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The choice to focus on "My Driving App" stems from its ability to address current inefficiencies in booking driving classes. It responds directly to the market's need for a more streamlined scheduling process, offering unique features like real-time updates on class availability and simplified date confirmations. These innovations set it apart from traditional methods and make it appealing to driving schools seeking to modernize. By highlighting its comprehensive benefits and user-friendly design, the app is poised to meet the increasing demand for technology-driven solutions that improve service efficiency. Its customer-centric approach ensures an intuitive experience that meets users' expectations for convenient and dependable scheduling of driving lessons (Early & Bubb, 2014).

The user envisions a transformative e-booking system for driving classes that eradicates the inefficiencies and frustrations of the current manual booking process. In this dream, students can seamlessly access a digital platform where they can easily view available class sessions, select their preferred dates, and make reservations without the hassle of waiting times or miscommunications (Alida, 2022). This user-friendly system would empower students to plan their driving lessons effectively, fostering a sense of autonomy and confidence in their learning journey. For the staff, the dream is of a streamlined and efficient process where they no longer need to individually contact students about class vacancies or deal with scheduling conflicts.

The ebooking system would provide a comprehensive tool for managing class schedules, accepting reservations, and ensuring a smooth flow of operations. This innovation promises to reduce administrative burdens, enhance communication, and optimize the overall scheduling and teaching processes. Ultimately, the dream is to create a harmonious and efficient environment at the Driving Institute Machang Sdn. Bhd., where technology bridges the gap between students' needs and staff's operational requirements, leading to an enhanced learning experience and improved organizational efficiency.

3. FINDINGS

The group generated considerable and varied outcomes for the e-booking for driving class project. First, the group successfully created a user-friendly and efficient e-booking system for driving classes. This technology allows students to simply register, check available class schedules, and book their preferred slots online, making the process easier and more accessible. In addition to the web-based system, the group created a mobile application that improves the user experience by showing real-time information about their next driving classes. The application gives users reminders and updates to help them manage their schedules more successfully. The app also includes push notifications for upcoming lessons, quick access to booking history, and the opportunity to reschedule or cancel classes with a few clicks.

Furthermore, the company implemented a feedback system on both the web and mobile platforms, allowing students to rate their instructors and remark on their experiences. This tool improves the quality of driving instruction and guarantees that instructors maintain good teaching standards. Comprehensive data security measures were also incorporated into the project to safeguard users' private information and guarantee the privacy of their booking information. The team implemented safe login procedures, encrypted data storage, and frequent system updates in accordance with best practices in cybersecurity. The project's total results, which include e-booking for driving classes, greatly improve user experience overall and accelerate the booking process, making it simpler and more effective for students to schedule their driving lessons.

4. DISCUSSION

Project Challenges:

4.1 Resource Constraints

Creating an online booking system for driving lessons is a difficult task, especially when it comes to limited resources (Othman et al., 2020). The project has to manage constrained funds, constrained schedules, and maybe limited human resources. It is essential to manage these limitations well in order to keep the project on schedule, fulfill deadlines, and provide a high-caliber system. This calls for meticulous planning, task prioritization, and perhaps the search for innovative alternatives, including utilizing open-source technologies or contracting out particular development work. Through careful resource allocation and transparent stakeholder and team communication, the project may minimize the risks related to resource constraints and maximize its development process.

4.2 User Acceptance

Ensuring broad user approval among staff and students is crucial to the e-booking system's success. Adoption may be limited by resistance to change, unfamiliarity with digital platforms, or insufficient training. Proactive change management techniques, clear e-booking interface design, and extensive user training programs are required to address these issues. Prior to complete deployment, issues can be found and fixed with the assistance of user testing, iterative feedback gathering, and early stakeholder engagement in the development process. Positive attitudes toward the e-booking system and its smooth incorporation into daily operations can be fostered by the project team by highlighting the advantages of the new system, such as greater schedule flexibility and simpler booking processes.

4.3 Project Success Indicators

4.3.1 Adoption and Engagement of Users

The rate of user adoption and engagement will be one of the primary indicators of success. A large number of users who have registered, regularly logins, and active registrations and bookings are evidence that the system is fulfilling the needs of the students. Insights into the adoption and usage of the mobile application can also be obtained by tracking the quantity of downloads and active users.

4.3.2 User Feedback and Satisfaction Gathering and Evaluating User Input

User Feedback and Satisfaction Gathering and evaluating user input will be important. User satisfaction will be indicated by favourable reviews, high ratings, and helpful criticism on the mobile application as well as the web-based system. To obtain comprehensive information regarding user experiences and opportunities for development, periodic surveys and feedback forms might be employed.

4.3.3 Administrative and Instructor Feedback Administrative staff and driving teachers' opinions

Administrative and Instructor Feedback Administrative staff and driving teachers' opinions will also be crucial. Positive feedback regarding how simple it is to manage schedules, how much less work there is for administrators, and how well students are communicated with will show that the system works well for all parties involved. Staff members' concerns and potential improvement areas can be found by holding regular meetings and feedback sessions.

5. CONCLUSION

The project's goal was to create a digital booking and scheduling system for Driving Institute Machang Sdn. Bhd. that was user-friendly, effective, and safe. Students were able to register, check available schedules, book their favourite times, and manage their classes with ease due to the mobile app that were included. The approach combined data security measures to safeguard personal information with feedback tools to maintain excellent teaching standards. The project is important because it will improve overall operational efficiency and user happiness by streamlining the booking process, minimising errors, and reducing scheduling conflicts. The project effectively tackled the obstacles of restricted funding, constrained timeframes, and a small workforce by employing strategic planning, effective resource management, and inventive approaches such as the utilisation of open-source technologies.

High user adoption rates, better operational efficiency, and an improved user experience are some of the practical consequences. Positive feedback was obtained, and the project's substantial reduction in booking errors demonstrated its usefulness. However, the idea has disadvantages, such as potential user resistance when switching from existing booking systems. Furthermore, achieving widespread adoption of the e-booking system among staff and students required extensive user training and early involvement. Future upgrades could include improving the user interface and experience, incorporating advanced features like adaptive learning, and expanding the system's functionality based on user feedback and changing demands.

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